

**ETHICS, RELIGION, AND SOCIETY: THE ROLE OF NATURAL LAW AND
BIBLICAL ETHICS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ETHICAL AND MORAL
FRAMEWORKS IN SOCIETY**

By

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Ethics, Religion, and Society: The Role of Natural Law and Biblical Ethics in the Development of Ethical and Moral Frameworks in Society¹

The world is facing an unprecedented time of turbulence due to political upheavals, polarizations, wars, racial tensions, protests, and claims of racial injustice. In order to restore peace and prosperity, people groups need to embrace strong ethical values and the principle human convictions of solidarity, mutual respect, and empathy. All of us agree on certain aspects of morals despite the differences in race, religion, and region. All of us affirm that human rights and justice are important because humans intuitively know that they deserve dignity and equal rights for life. How do the natural law philosophical foundations and biblical ethics contribute to the moral consensus in the pluralistic society?

In this article, an argument will be made on how the natural-law foundations and biblical ethics contribute significantly to moral consensus in the society, specifically in relation to ethics and justice. First, the philosophical foundation of natural law theory will be explained. Second, the role of the Bible in the development of social ethics will be discussed. Third, how moral consensus is possible without a religious foundation will be explained. At last, the practical question of if lies are ever justified as a case of applying contextual ethics to the contemporary social and political dilemma will be examined.

Natural Law Theory: Value and Its Applications in Society

The legitimate institutions and structures like marriage, family, morals, civil laws, social laws, governments, and political structures exist in the history of mankind apart from Judeo-Christian civilization and special revelation. Human beings share common values, morals, behaviors, rituals, laws, and governing principles, with some exceptions and degrees of variation.

¹ This article is a composition of previously written assignments — including essay and reflections — for the course “Christian Ethics,” taught by Dr. Andrew Walker at Southern Baptist Theological Seminary, Louisville, KY.

For example, murder without a lawful excuse is considered a crime in most cultures. The natural law theory provides the philosophical and theological explanation for good attributes, legitimate institutions, and common grace across the cultures and in the entirety of human history.

First, natural law is defined as the order or rule of human behavior based on human nature as created by God, knowable by all men through human intuition and reasoning alone, and normative for all human beings. Natural law is not dependent on any divine revelation.² Natural law is distinct from both God's eternal law and human law in that God's eternal law is the basis for natural law, just as the purpose of the invention is determined by the mind of the inventor.³ On the other hand, human law is constructed by the application of reason to general principles for the common good. Human law relies on natural law; therefore, natural law is the foundation for it.⁴ Although natural law is imposed on creatures, it is not mechanistic or without exception.

Second, natural law is affirmed by biblical and theological evidence. God has revealed something about his character, morals, and creation to all humans, including people in other religions (Acts 14:17). This general revelation is given to all humanity apart from the revelation of scriptures.⁵ David Haines and Andrew A. Fulford argue that the first pronouncement of good in Genesis about the good created order proclaims the natural law in creation.⁶ In Exodus 18:17-18, Jethro instructed Moses to appoint multiple leaders to lead the congregation of Israel efficiently. Jethro was a non-Israelite who did not have prior knowledge of Mosaic law. However, his instruction is wise and useful, and it helped Moses when there was no divine

² David Haines and Andrew A. Fulford, *Natural Law: A Brief Introduction and Biblical Defense*. (Russia: Davenant Institute, 2017), 5.

³ Haines and Fulford, *Natural Law*, 7.

⁴ Haines and Fulford, 8.

⁵ J. Budziszewski, *Written on the Heart: The Case for Natural Law*, (Downers Grove, Ill: InterVarsity Press, 1997), 180-181.

⁶ Haines and Fulford, 51.

instruction.⁷ Similarly, the authors of the New Testament affirm that God ordained natural law in the world and he appointed the rulers and governments. In Romans 13:1-4, Paul argues that God ordained the political order in the world, and to disobey the government is to disobey God.⁸

Third, natural law is a great resource and helpful tool because of its potential use for social issues. If natural law is ordained for all human beings, it has normative implications for society. Natural law positions certain moral constraints on the legitimate structures of institutional life.⁹ Natural law theory is a critical reflective account of human institutions, communities, and their well-being. Natural law theory intends to recognize principles of right action, including human rights and human dignity. Humans inherently possess certain rights, and governments are bound to protect those rights based on their nature as humans.¹⁰ This argument forms the basis for equality, justice, rights of education and healthcare, and rights of protection from murder, slavery, and mistreatment. If humans have inalienable rights by virtue of their humanity, this applies to embryonic and unborn babies; therefore, they should be protected by the norm against the killing of the innocent.¹¹ These principles could be applied to the institutions of marriage, civil, and judiciary authorities. Paul affirmed natural law truths concerning the decency of marriage, the authority of parents over children, and the condemnation of extramarital sexual affairs (1 Corinthians 7). Paul also acknowledges the natural law obligation of society to secure justice through civil authorities.¹²

⁷ Haines and Fulford, 54.

⁸ Haines and Fulford, 101.

⁹ Jean Porter, *Natural and Divine Law: Reclaiming the Tradition for Christian Ethics*. (Ottawa, Ontario: Novalis, 1999), 250.

¹⁰ Robert P. George, *Natural Law and Evangelical Political Thought*, ed. Bryan T McGraw, Jesse David Covington, and Micah Joel Watson (Lanham, Maryland: Lexington Books, 2013), 111.

¹¹ George, *Natural Law and Evangelical Political Thought*, 112-113.

¹² George, 100-101.

Role of the Bible in the Development of Ethics

In a culture of moral confusion and political-cultural war, what role does religion play in securing a reliable ethical framework for its proponents to assimilate and participate in the ethical and moral discussions? Christians rely on both the Old Testament and the New Testament as their ground for modern ethics. The primary premises for ethical arguments in the Old Testament are the moral character of God and his demands for moral righteousness and justice (Lev 21:8, Isa 1:17). The New Testament proposes love, forgiveness, and charity as moral principles. Despite the sophisticated ethical grounding and moral value of biblical ethics, one needs to pay attention to the historical context and cultural limitations of the Old Testament and the New Testament before one applies the ethics of the Bible to modern society.

First, the worldview of Israelites needs to be understood in order to understand the relationship of Israelites with God and their social, cultural, and civil values. Christopher J. H. Wright emphasized that theology and ethics are inseparable, and it is difficult to alienate the values and ethics of Israelites from their faith and beliefs about God. Wright explained the worldview of Israelites as follows: God has created the world, and he is the owner of it; humans are made in the image of God; humans rebelled against God and brought disruptions in the relationship; and God has a plan of redemption that begins with Abraham, father of Israel, and then extends to all the nations. Wright pointed out the three pillars of Israel's worldview: God (theological perspective), Israel (social perspective), and the land (economic perspective).¹³ To Israel, God is one, and there is no one else beside him. His acts revealed him and his character as the true God. When Israelites served other gods and worshipped them, it was counted as an ethical sin apart from religious sin. God acted in the history of Israel to bring redemption, make a

¹³ Christopher J. H. Wright, *Old Testament Ethics for the People of God* (Downers Grove, Illinois: InterVarsity Press, 2004) 17-19.

covenant, and build his relationship with them.¹⁴ Israelites are bound to obey God's revealed will in his Word and align themselves with God's social, civil, and political ethical norms.¹⁵ The social structure of Israel is unique in that YHWH is their ultimate king, and it is God who owns the land and distributes it to people and demands justice. All aspects of life, including land ownership, sexuality, fertility, marriage, and social and religious affairs, are under the authority of God.¹⁶

Second, the content of Old Testament ethics and its limitations needs to be understood before applying it to Christians. Holiness is supremely important in all areas of life for Israelites because their God is holy (Lev 11:45). The moral nature, character, and commands of Yahweh are the ground for the Old Testament ethics. The call for holiness separates them from other nations. Contemporary biblical ethicists believe that holiness is one of the fundamental themes of Old Testament ethics.¹⁷ Holiness in the family and society is important. Marriage was instituted by God; he ordained the union of male and female to bear the children and subdue the earth. God established the norm of human family life (Gen 2:4). Marriage is a covenant act made before God and society. Children are expected to honor their parents.¹⁸ Old Testament ethics include the foundations, governing principles, and laws for social ethics and justice. Humans are inherently worthy of dignity and respect, as they are made in the image of God (Gen 1:26-27). It is a deliberate sin and violation of law to murder a human (Ex 20:13). It is a sin to harden the heart against a poor brother (Deut 15:7-11). God rebuked injustice and acts of mistreatment and taking fraudulent advantage of the poor. God's people are expected to give heed to widows and

¹⁴ Wright, *Old Testament Ethics for the People of God*, 24-25.

¹⁵ Wright, 30-31.

¹⁶ Wright, 67-68.

¹⁷ Walter C. Kaiser, *Toward Old Testament Ethics* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 1983), 139-141.

¹⁸ Kaiser, *Toward Old Testament Ethics*, 154-155.

orphans.¹⁹ In spite of the extensive rich treasures of ethics in the Old Testament, there are some limitations. The Old Testament law is primarily given to Israelites only (Deut 23:3). In that sense, there is a nationalistic limitation. The historical and cultural limitations prevented people from obeying the standards of the law. God did not deliberately condemn slavery, polygamy, and low views of women when they were reported in the Old Testament due to the historical and cultural limitations. There is a legalistic limitation to applying the law because humans are imperfect in obeying the law. The materialistic limitation of the law is true because the law itself did not compartmentalize the spiritual and material life. However, the spiritual aspect of the law is evident when one understands the nature of God, his holy commandments, and his ordinances for family, social, and political life.²⁰

Third, biblical ethics, including the Old Testament laws, are extremely resourceful and valuable when one correctly applies them. Protestants applied the law for three basic purposes: social use, convictional use, and normative use. The law acts as a restraint against human sin and social evil. The law convicts human sin by reflecting on God's standards and his expectations for his image-bearers. It acts as a lamp to the feet in guiding and training people in moral righteousness. There are three approaches in applying all the law: discontinuity, continuity, and semi-continuity.²¹ There is a discontinuity in the sense that certain laws, like ceremonial and civil laws, are not applicable to us. Since the Old Covenant is not operative after the coming of Christ, Christians are not bound to the Old Covenant in a legalistic sense. However, the church lives in a new covenant age,²² and the church is expected to obey their Lord. On the other hand, the basic

¹⁹ Kaiser, *Toward Old Testament Ethics*, 159-161.

²⁰ Kaiser, 34-37.

²¹ David W. Jones, *An Introduction to Biblical Ethics*. ed. Daniel R Heimbach (Nashville, TN: B&H Academic, 2013), 78-79.

²² Thomas R. Schreiner, *40 Questions About Christians and Biblical Law* (Grand Rapids, MI: Kregel Publications, 2010), 71.

ethical and moral principles behind all the laws are still applicable. Calvin and Luther believed that there are moral norms found in the Old Testament and they are useful for the instruction and development of Christian ethics.²³ At last, when the church preaches and teaches the laws, it grounds them in the new light of the gospel and principles in the New Testament.²⁴ Christianity played a crucial role in the historical moral, legal, and ethical frameworks because of its historical, social, and religious primacy in Western civilization and the colonial world. Biblical ethics are still valuable resources in the ongoing modern ethical and moral discussions because Christian ethics are grounded in the historical cultural realities and experiences of pluralistic societies.

Religious Foundation and Moral Consensus in Society

It is possible for humans to achieve sufficient moral consensus without a religious foundation. When some groups appeal for justice, equality, and human rights, they are appealing to the larger culture in spite of the differences in their religions and political stances.

First, a religious foundation is not essential for Christians to live peacefully and promote morality in the world. Christians should learn to live with a larger culture that does not have a religious foundation. Christians are minorities in most countries where there is no Christian foundation for politics. By the very definition, politics is the art of living together in the community.²⁵ John Stott defines politics as “the process whereby a group of people, whose opinions or interests are divergent, reach collective decisions which are binding on the whole

²³ Schreiner, *40 Questions About Christians and Biblical Law*, 99.

²⁴ Schreiner, 229.

²⁵ Mark W. Charlton, *Christian Worldview and the Academic Disciplines: Crossing the Academy*, ed. Downey, Deane E.D, and Stanley E Porter (Eugene: Pickwick Publications, 2009), 405.

group and enforced as common policy.”²⁶ According to this definition, politics assumes a diversity of views on the goals for the community and methods to achieve those goals. Consensus on every political issue is not possible when the community is composed of diverse value systems with religions and non-religions. However, Christians can still strive for justice, liberty, and equality for all people by persuasion, promotion, and persistence. Martin Luther King Jr. is a classic example of how to transform a culture by fighting against injustice. He led a non-violent civil rights movement and called for legal, economic, educational, and attitudinal change. He championed civil rights for African Americans, and he strove for the forgiveness and reconciliation of Black and White races.²⁷

Second, a theonomy is not an answer to the broken culture.²⁸ Although many Christians desire to seek out a theonomy for achieving moral consensus, it is not achievable and also does not guarantee a biblical model for government. Theonomy is a hypothetical government form in which the Mosaic covenant is applied to the current political government. The problem with theonomy is that it is not based on careful biblical exegesis. It confuses the boundaries between church and state and degenerates religious distinctiveness. Although it correctly understands and applies the moral force of Mosaic civil law, it fails to understand the discontinuity of the old covenant and the inauguration of the new covenant with the hope of an already and not yet kingdom. It seeks glory in the present age. Theonomy undermines God’s eternal law revealed in natural law. The Christendom in medieval Europe did not yield a just society; on the other hand, it brought disrepute on Christianity for the moral failures of church

²⁶ Charlton, *Christian Worldview and the Academic Disciplines*, 405-406.

²⁷ Craig A Carter, *Rethinking Christ and Culture: A Post-Christendom Perspective* (Grand Rapids: Brazos Press, 2006), 190.

²⁸ Andrew T. Walker, “American Culture Is Broken. Is Theonomy the Answer?” *The Gospel Coalition*, March 2021, <https://www.thegospelcoalition.org/article/theonomy/>.

and state. At last, the Bible did not endorse a theonomy in the state; rather, it mandates Christians to be subjected to their political government and pray for the rulers in that government.²⁹

Third, natural law provides the basis for Christians to seek moral consensus from the rulers and culture.³⁰ Natural law is a moral theory that affirms that God gave a universal moral order in creation that governs our reasoning and behavior. Andrew Walker pointed out that natural law implies that humans are capable of comprehending which actions are good and eminently reasonable without appealing to God's word. Natural law provides the basis for morality for all people. Walker argued that politicians can govern justly without committing the state to a formal religious or philosophical obligation. Henry underscored that the role of government is not to judge between philosophical systems and establish one among others. According to him, the government's role is to ensure and secure a free course for everyone. It does not lead to moral neutrality; rather, it allows the government to not rely on one religious or nonreligious system.³¹

At last, scriptures suggest that a religious foundation is not necessary for a moral consensus in society. In Romans 2:14-15, Paul explained that gentiles are capable of distinguishing good from evil without the knowledge of God's word, and they show that the law is written in their hearts. This law is nothing but God's natural law given to humanity. In Romans 13:1-7, Paul admonished that Christians should subject themselves to governing authorities, and he emphasized that all authorities and human governments are instituted by the sovereign plan of God. He underscored that if someone is resisting the authorities, in a sense, they are resisting God. This admonition implies that human governments and rulers are equipped with moral

²⁹ Walker, "American Culture Is Broken."

³⁰ Andrew T. Walker, *Liberty for All: Defending Everyone's Religious Freedom in a Pluralistic Age* (United States: Baker Publishing Group, 2021), 36.

³¹ Walker, *Liberty for All*, 37-38.

knowledge through natural law. There was no appeal given to Christians to fight for religious conversions of the rulers or seek a religious government. In Matthew 22:17-22, Jesus clarifies that Christians are expected to give taxes to rulers, as it belongs to them, and humans are expected to serve God, as they belong to him as image-bearers. Religious affairs are distinct from civil and political affairs.³²

The presence of injustice and inequality in society is possible due to corruption and imbalanced economic structures despite the natural law. When the state fails to administer justice, Christians as a religious group play a crucial role in reminding and persuading the authorities, policy makers, and rulers to act justly for the common good of all people.

Conclusion

First, the natural law theory serves as a philosophical foundation for moral consensus, justice, ethical guidance, and social engagement. Humans inherently possess certain non-alienable rights, and governments are expected to secure them based on their nature as humans. The natural law theory serves as a basis for equality, justice, rights of education and healthcare, and rights of protection from murder, slavery, and mistreatment. Second, the Bible is a valuable source for instruction, guidance, and learning. The powerful narratives and moral stories equip Christians to uphold ethical values and live peacefully with their neighbors. Both the Old Testament and the New Testament serve as valuable tools for the development of Christian ethics. Third, a religious foundation is not necessary for the moral consensus in society, as God imbedded natural law in his creation to distinguish what is good for human flourishing. Christians should learn to live with a larger culture that does not have a religious foundation and

³² Walker, *Liberty for All*, 38-41.

strive to promote biblical values in that culture. A theonomy is evidently not an answer to the broken culture.

Case Study for Contextual Ethics: Is Lying Ever Justified in a Political Dilemma?

One of the significant challenges that trouble philosophers and Christian thinkers is if they should uphold the truth ethic or love ethic, especially when they deal with the political and social issues. Is lying ever permitted in some scenarios, and what is considered a lie? Many organizations struggle to apply the contextual ethics when they are called to serve the vulnerable people in marginalized communities and politically sensitive places. In this case study, some scenarios will be examined where leaders need to apply contextual ethics instead of legalistic fundamental ethics. The act of lying is permitted in some circumstances when one is not expected to tell the truth. However, one should be cautious in not endorsing a lie for the sake of personal interests, to fulfill selfish mottos, to pursue evil and deception, and to oppress people. An argument can be made to permit a lie in order to protect lives and fulfill a higher good.

First, religious ethics do not permit the casual treatment of telling lies. Since God is absolute truth, he always speaks and acts in truth, and he expects that his people should always speak the truth (Num 23:19, Zech 8:16, Prov 12:17, and Eph 4:15). However, there are instances in the Bible where people lied to protect life (Exod 1:17-20), support God's people (Josh 2), and protect their own lives (2 Kgs 6:19). This raises some questions—is lying ever justified, and what is a lie? The word “lie” should be carefully defined to avoid confusion with falsehood, deception, and tricks. Charles Hodge suggested that not every act of deception is a lie in terms of morality. According to him, a lie includes an intention to deceive when one is supposed to and bound to tell the truth.³³ Full disclosure is not always expected, and a trick or deception is

³³ Davis, *Evangelical Ethics*, 11.

inevitable. For example, a sports person is not always bound to reveal his game. Rahab had no obligation to speak the truth when she was under the authority of a new king.³⁴ In a similar vein, Sam Storms argued that not all falsehoods are lies. According to him, a lie is an intentional deception that disregards someone's right to know the truth. In times of war and criminal assaults, people are not obligated to tell the truth to the enemy. He defined a lie as follows: "A lie is the intentional declaration or communication of a falsehood designed to deceive someone who has a moral and legal right to know the truth."³⁵ On the other hand, Grudem pointed out that "lying is affirming in a speech or writing something you believe to be false."³⁶

Second, scriptures reveal that God's people lied, concealed the truth, or provided false information in certain circumstances to protect the lives, support God's people, and preserve their own lives. They were not bound to tell the truth morally because of the unwarranted sinful pressure and to avoid a higher evil. For example, Egyptian midwives lied to protect babies in Exodus 1:17-20. They were not condemned for their deception. Instead, God showed favor to them (Exodus 1:20).³⁷ While God did not approve of their lie by any means, he approved of their obedience in protecting the babies, and his overall affirmation is evident. God did not prescribe a lie here; however, one could make the argument that God did not condemn it either. Similarly, Rahab had hidden the spies of Israel and lied to the king of Jericho (Judges 2:1-5). It is understandable that she lied in order to show her allegiance to Israel's God, and she demonstrated her faith (Hebrews 11:31). John Jefferson Davis pointed out that one human life is

³⁴ Davis, *Evangelical Ethics*, 11.

³⁵ Samuel C. Storms, *Tough Topics 2: Biblical Answers to 25 Challenging Questions* (Fearn, Ross-shire, Scotland, Great Britain: Christian Focus Publications, 2015), 254-255.

³⁶ Wayne A. Grudem, *Christian Ethics: An Introduction to Biblical Moral Reasoning* (Wheaton, Illinois: Crossway, 2018), 311.

³⁷ Sam Storms, "Perplexing Passages: Do Exodus 1 and Joshua 2 Permit Christians to Lie? *TGC* (January 25, 2018), <https://www.thegospelcoalition.org/article/perplexing-passages-do-exodus-1-and-joshua-2-permit-christians-to-lie/>.

more important in God's sight than the entire world. He argued that her higher duty to protect God's servants prevented the *prima facie duty* to tell the truth, and her course of action was acceptable to God.³⁸ In a similar vein, John Frame argued that people have no obligation to tell the truth to people who seek innocent life.³⁹ In spite of the differences in semantics, a lie is either not addressed, or it is pardoned, or it is not a lie at all in these circumstances.⁴⁰

At last, the argument for not telling lies under all circumstances needs to be addressed. Augustine argued that one should never lie at all, since no examples of lies deserving imitation are found in the habits and deeds of saints.⁴¹ In a similar vein, Grudem argued that "...lying is always wrong in every situation and every circumstance of life, and this will be true for all eternity."⁴² Although Augustine and Grudem insist that lying is always a sin and one should never lie, there should be genuine situations and occasions when deception or lying should be permissible.⁴³ God shows compassion and pardons the people who lie in critical situations, as he did to the Egyptian midwives and Rahab. However, lying should never be affirmed or endorsed. Christians should not be casual in their treatment of truth, even in the small areas.⁴⁴

In a general sense, a lie is not acceptable because it is contrary to the biblical commands and cultural expectations. However, Charles Hodge suggested that not every act of deception is a lie in terms of morality. According to him, a lie includes an intention to deceive when one is

³⁸ Davis, *Evangelical Ethics*, 10.

³⁹ Grudem, *Christian Ethics*, 326.

⁴⁰ Davis, *Evangelical Ethics*, 11.

⁴¹ Augustine, Roy J Deferrari, and Mary Sarah Muldowney. *Treatises on Various Subjects: The Christian Life, Lying, against Lying, Continenence, Patience, the Excellence of Widowhood, the Work of Monks, the Usefulness of Fasting, the Eight Questions of Dulcitus*, Fathers of the Church, a New Translation, V. 16 (repr., Washington, DC: Catholic University of America Press, 2002), 107.

⁴² Grudem, *Christian Ethics*, 332.

⁴³ Storms, *Tough Topics 2*, 255.

⁴⁴ Storms, 255.

supposed and bound to tell the truth. In certain circumstances, the Bible did not condemn people for telling lies, as some of them did it to protect lives (Exod 1:17-20), support God's people (Josh 2), and protect their own lives (2 Kgs 6:19). As argued by John Frame, people have no moral obligation to tell the truth in certain circumstances. What it means for the leaders today who are defending the lives of marginalized communities, suffering people, and persecuted nations. The leaders need to tactfully deal with the situations and help the vulnerable without giving into the temptations of legalism and fundamentalistic beliefs. The priority is to protect the rights of the vulnerable, the sanctity of human life, and the common good of all people. However, lies should not be treated casually, especially if they are used for personal profit.

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